

THEORY AND METHODOLOGY OF VOCATIONAL EDUCATION

UDK 378:37.091.3:646.7

DOI <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17092106>

Innovative approaches to teaching blond techniques in the professional training of salon service specialists

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Accepted: 26.08.2025 | Published: 10.09.2025

***Abstract.** The relevance of this study is determined by the need to modernize professional education in the field of salon services, which necessitates the introduction of modern educational technologies and teaching methods that align with the trends of the beauty industry. Traditional approaches to training hairdressers do not sufficiently account for the dynamics of new techniques and the need to develop creative and entrepreneurial competencies. One such area is the teaching of blonding methods, which requires special attention during professional training due to their technological complexity, high popularity among clients, and significant impact on a specialist's competitiveness. The **purpose** of the article is to provide theoretical justification and practical analysis of innovative approaches to teaching blonding methods in the professional training of salon service specialists and to identify effective pedagogical solutions for improving the quality of education. The research employs a range of **methods**, including the analysis of scientific and methodological literature on professional education and the beauty industry, as well as a comparative analysis of traditional and innovative educational*

*practices. The **study's results** indicate that integrating innovative methods into the training of salon service specialists leads to a higher level of professional motivation, fosters the development of critical thinking, and enhances the readiness of future professionals to work in real-world practice conditions. In particular, the use of virtual learning platforms and video content significantly expands the opportunities for students to work independently. At the same time, workshops and practice-oriented tasks facilitate the development of stable professional skills. The **conclusions** emphasize that innovative approaches to teaching blonding methods in professional education are a key factor in enhancing the competitiveness of salon service specialists in the labor market. Promising directions for further research are identified, including the development of authorial curricula, the improvement of integrated forms of practical training, and the expansion of opportunities for digital educational resources. Special emphasis is placed on the importance of combining innovative teaching technologies with traditional training methods, which ensures the comprehensiveness and systematic development of professional competencies.*

Keywords: *professional education, salon service, competence-based approach, workshop, digital technologies.*

Інноваційні підходи до викладання блонд-методик у професійній підготовці майстрів салонного сервісу

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Анотація. *Актуальність дослідження зумовлена необхідністю модернізації професійної освіти у сфері салонного сервісу, яка вимагає впровадження сучасних освітніх технологій і методик викладання, що*

відповідають тенденціям розвитку індустрії краси. Традиційні підходи до підготовки майстрів-перукарів недостатньо враховують динаміку появи нових технік і потребу у формуванні креативних та підприємницьких компетентностей. Одним із таких напрямів є навчання блонд-методик, що потребує особливої уваги у процесі професійної підготовки через їхню технологічну складність, високу популярність серед клієнтів та значний вплив на конкурентоспроможність майстра. **Метою** статті є теоретичне обґрунтування й практичний аналіз інноваційних підходів до викладання блонд-методик у професійній підготовці майстрів салонного сервісу та визначення ефективних педагогічних рішень для підвищення якості навчання. У дослідженні застосовано комплекс **методів**: аналіз науково-методичної літератури з проблем професійної освіти й індустрії краси, порівняльний аналіз традиційних та інноваційних освітніх практик. **Результати** дослідження свідчать, що інтеграція інноваційних методів у процес підготовки майстрів салонного сервісу забезпечує більш високий рівень професійної мотивації, сприяє розвитку критичного мислення та підвищує готовність майбутніх фахівців до роботи в умовах реальної практики. Зокрема, використання віртуальних навчальних платформ та відеоконтенту значно розширює можливості самостійної роботи здобувачів освіти, тоді як майстер-класи та практико орієнтовані завдання дозволяють формувати стабільні професійні навички. **Висновки.** Інноваційні підходи до викладання блонд-методик у професійній освіті є ключовим чинником підвищення конкурентоспроможності майстрів салонного сервісу на ринку праці. Визначено перспективні напрями подальших досліджень, що пов'язані з розробкою авторських програмних курсів, удосконаленням інтегрованих форм практичного навчання та розширенням можливостей цифрових освітніх ресурсів. Особливий акцент зроблено на важливості поєднання інноваційних

технологій навчання з традиційними формами підготовки, що забезпечує комплексність та системність формування професійної компетентності.

***Ключові слова:** професійна освіта, салонний сервіс, компетентнісний підхід, майстер-клас, цифрові технології.*

Problem statement. The sphere of professional education in the field of salon services is currently undergoing active transformations, driven by the rapid development of the beauty industry, increasing competitive requirements in the labor market, and the need to implement modern educational technologies. The traditional system of training master hairdressers often fails to align with the dynamics of emerging new techniques and methods, which reduces the effectiveness of developing practical skills and creative competencies in applicants. In this context, the training of blond methods deserves special attention, which is distinguished by technological complexity and high demand among clients.

Even though elements of interactive technologies, digital platforms and practice-oriented approaches are increasingly used in the educational process, the problem of integrating innovative teaching methods in the field of blond methods remains insufficiently researched. At the same time, practice highlights the limitations of existing pedagogical models and the lack of methodological recommendations that take into account the specifics of forming professional competencies in this area.

Thus, the relevance of the study lies in the need for scientifically based analysis and the development of innovative approaches to teaching blond techniques, which will enable the combination of traditional forms of education with the latest technologies, ensuring high-quality training of salon service masters and increasing their competitiveness in the modern labor market.

Analysis of recent studies and publications. The issue of innovative approaches in the professional training of future salon service masters has been the

focus of attention of domestic and foreign researchers in recent years. This is due to the rapid development of the beauty industry, the emergence of new dyeing and color technologies, as well as the growing demand for high-quality educational practices in the field of training specialists.

Researchers emphasize the importance of introducing innovative technologies into the professional training of future service specialists. Thus, L. Korotkova emphasizes the role of educational and production clusters as an environment for integrating modern methods in the training of salon service masters [1]. Similar ideas are expressed by O. Vozniuk and T. Lekhitskyi, analyzing the impact of innovative teaching methods on the formation of the professional culture of education seekers [2].

Significant attention is paid to the methods of practice-oriented learning. In particular, M. Silaeva justifies the effectiveness of master classes in the professional training of hairdressers as a form of combining theory and practice [3]. In the same context, T. Leshchenko analyzes the use of the case method, which enables the activation of cognitive activity in future masters and brings the educational process closer to real production conditions [4].

No less important is the experience of using game technologies. Thus, M. Diachenko reveals the possibilities of gamification in hairdressing lessons, which helps to increase the motivation of education seekers and develop their practical skills [5].

Significant scientific interest is aroused by studies on the integration of digital and virtual technologies into the educational process. L. Shkurdoda proves the prospects of using virtual reality technologies in the system of vocational education, emphasizing their potential in practicing complex techniques [6]. A similar approach is reflected in the work of O. Horodetska, which considers the role of computer technologies in the professional activities of future master hairdressers [7].

The aspect of coloristic training is highlighted by O. Getman, emphasizing the importance of thorough mastery of the basics of color science for the formation of professional skills of future hairdressers [8]. A similar opinion on the integration of professional culture in the service sector under conditions of societal informatization is expressed by Y. Kozlovskiy, N. Mukan, and L. Zelman [9].

The focus of scientific attention is also the use of innovative educational technologies. O. Maksymovych emphasizes the need to train teachers and masters of industrial training to implement innovations in vocational education [10] actively. O. Khorzhevskaya and L. Danylenko raise similar issues, analyzing innovation processes in professional and practical training [11]. D. Synytsia draws attention to the need to form innovative activity as an integral element of the work of a master of industrial training [12].

Special attention should be paid to the formation of communicative and social competencies of future masters. In particular, D. Bilay explores the pedagogical principles of training hairdressers for productive business communication, emphasizing the need to develop skills of interaction with the client as a component of professional competence [13].

It is worth noting that foreign studies also focus on innovations in pedagogy. Thus, Chen Wang studies the role of digital media in the modernization of teaching methods in higher education [14]. At the same time, V. Nazarenko analyzes the evolution of visual identity in mass media through the lens of the development of the art of makeup [15], which has an indirect bearing on the formation of modern approaches in salon service.

Thus, the analysis reveals that previous scientific works encompass a wide range of aspects of professional training for future salon service masters, including the use of master classes, case methods, and game technologies, as well as the application of digital technologies, virtual reality, and communicative training. However, special studies explicitly devoted to innovative approaches to teaching

blonde techniques remain rare. The issues of integrating the latest color techniques into curricula, adapting digital and virtual technologies to the specifics of blonde coloring, and developing pedagogical models for the formation of students' comprehensive competencies in this area are insufficiently studied. This study is dedicated to filling these gaps.

Highlighting previously unresolved parts of the general problem. Despite the growing attention to the modernization of professional education in the field of salon services, the problem of implementing innovative approaches to teaching specialized technologies, particularly blond techniques, remains insufficiently studied. Existing scientific and methodological works primarily focus on general issues of developing the competencies of master hairdressers or the use of individual interactive tools. At the same time, the specifics of teaching blond techniques require deeper analysis.

The issue of effectively integrating digital simulators, virtual platforms, and video content into the process of developing professional skills, as well as determining the optimal balance between traditional forms of practice and innovative methods, remains open. The pedagogical conditions under which master classes and the case method will maximally contribute to the development of creativity and confidence of future specialists are insufficiently studied.

In addition, there are almost no methodological recommendations that would comprehensively combine various innovative approaches to teaching blonde techniques and take into account the modern needs of the beauty industry. It necessitates a scientific search for effective educational models that can ensure high-quality training and competitiveness among salon service masters.

Formulation of the article's objectives (task statement). The purpose of this article is to substantiate theoretically and practically analyze innovative approaches to teaching blonde techniques in the professional training of salon

service masters, as well as to determine pedagogical conditions that contribute to increasing the effectiveness of training.

To achieve this goal, the following tasks have been set:

- to analyze current trends in the development of professional education in the field of salon service and their impact on the training of hairdressers;
- to investigate the features of teaching blonde techniques using VR/AR, digital simulators, video content and programs for virtual image selection;
- compare traditional and innovative pedagogical methods (master classes, case method, game lessons, project and problem technologies) in terms of their effectiveness and impact on the development of practical and creative competencies;
- develop recommendations for integrating innovative methods into the educational process to increase motivation, professional training and competitiveness of future specialists.

The implementation of these tasks will allow to form a comprehensive vision of innovative learning blonde methods, expand pedagogical tools and contribute to improving the quality of professional education in the field of salon service.

Presentation of the main research material. Modern professional education in the field of salon service actively integrates innovative technologies and methods, allowing training of masters who are able to work effectively in a rapidly changing market. The combination of classic practical skills with digital tools, such as video lessons, simulators, and programs for virtual image modeling, enhances the quality of training and stimulates creativity, independence, and the ability to adapt to client needs. In current conditions, a salon service master must be not only technically educated and cultured, but also able to implement the latest trends quickly, possess professional skills and innovative technologies, particularly in the field of blond techniques, which require exceptional accuracy, a deep understanding of color, and proven practical skills. Analysis of modern trends reveals that students who study

using integrated methods master complex techniques more quickly, develop professional competencies, and demonstrate a higher level of motivation to study.

Modern innovative approaches to teaching blond techniques in the professional training of salon service masters open up new opportunities for the professional training of salon service masters. Training using modern techniques allows students to practice hair coloring techniques without risk to a real client, which significantly increases their confidence, accuracy and speed of performing procedures. Such practice serves as a kind of «simulator» before real application on clients.

At this stage of the development of the teaching process, traditional forms of teaching (lectures, demonstrations) are significantly inferior to innovative technologies in such criteria as the development of creativity, the level of student motivation and the quality of practical skills. This confirms the feasibility of integrating digital solutions into the professional training system for future master's students.

The summarized results are presented in Table 1, which reflects the key advantages of innovative approaches in teaching blond techniques in vocational education.

Table 1

Advantages of innovative approaches to teaching blonde techniques in the professional training of salon service masters

Type of innovation/method	Advantages in the context of training for blonde techniques
Virtual/augmented reality (VR/AR)	Safe practice, reduced fear of error, and realistic practice of techniques
Digital simulators/mannequins	Realistic experience, possibility of multiple repetition, and convenience in learning
Video content and online platforms	Independent practice of techniques, mobile learning, availability at any time
Master classes and case method	Consolidation of skills, development of creative thinking, and formation of practical competence

Type of innovation/method	Advantages in the context of training for blonde techniques
Interactive formats (discussions, groups)	Increasing motivation, exchange of experience, and feedback
Game method (game lessons, role-playing games)	Creating emotional involvement, developing communication skills, and modeling real situations of working with clients
Project technologies	Formation of research skills, development of responsibility, and obtaining a real practical result
Modeling of professional activity (production tasks, simulation exercises)	Awareness of the professional context, working out algorithms of actions in difficult situations
Problem-based learning	Development of creative and critical thinking, ability to find solutions in non-standard dyeing conditions
Interactive methods (brainstorming, aquarium, large circle)	Collective search for ideas, development of cooperation skills, and generation of non-standard approaches
Technologies for solving creative and inventive tasks	Formation of associative thinking, the ability to predict results and see alternative solutions
Software for virtual image selection (Cosmopolitan, Teleport)	Safe testing of hair color, reduction of the risk of errors when choosing a shade, individualization of the approach to the client

Source: author's development

The use of virtual reality (VR) technologies presents new opportunities in the professional training of salon service masters, particularly in teaching blonde techniques. Since working with hair lightening requires maximum accuracy, a deep understanding of color and the development of practical skills are essential. VR technologies are becoming an effective tool for safely practicing professional techniques.

Firstly, in a virtual environment, it is possible to simulate procedures when students practice various techniques of dyeing, toning or lightening hair without the risk of spoiling the result and without additional costs for materials. Secondly, VR allows you to simulate working with clients, modeling different hair types, color requests and individual characteristics, which forms the ability of future hairdressers to quickly respond to the needs of the customer.

In addition, VR technologies are effectively used in teaching safety techniques: from the correct use of hot tools to compliance with sanitary and hygienic standards. No less important is the aspect of creativity development, as students get the opportunity to experiment with shades of blonde dyes, combine different styles and create complex color solutions without time and material restrictions.

Thus, VR technologies become an innovative educational tool that contributes to the formation of professional confidence, the development of creative thinking and the improvement of practical skills in the field of blonde techniques [6, p. 202].

A crucial innovative tool in teaching blonde techniques are digital mannequins with realistically modeled hair. They provide exercises in styling and coloring that closely simulate real-world conditions, which enhances the quality of knowledge consolidation and allows students to improve their skills without incurring additional material costs.

The use of video content and online platforms presents new opportunities for the professional training of salon service masters. Thanks to these tools, students can independently practice techniques at a pace convenient for them, which increases the efficiency of learning the material. The mobility of learning allows for combining practice with work or other educational processes, as access to video lessons is possible at any time and from any device. Thus, online resources form an individual learning trajectory and contribute to the development of independence and responsibility skills, which are necessary for a modern specialist in the field of salon service.

One effective way to improve the professional skills of future hairdressers is through a master class. In the context of training salon service specialists, a master class is considered an open event that demonstrates modern methods for performing blond dyeing techniques, haircuts, and styling [3, p. 395]. The main task of this form of learning is not only to transfer knowledge, but also to demonstrate productive

methods of activity: methods, techniques and technologies that allow students to master creative approaches to performing professional tasks.

The master class is designed to foster students' independence, creative thinking, and motivation for self-improvement. The organization of such a lesson involves working with practical tasks, choosing tools and methods for performing procedures, and modeling various situations when working with clients. Students have the opportunity to work out their own solutions, discuss them with colleagues and adjust the results in accordance with the experience gained. This process includes the stages of «deconstruction» and «reconstruction», where the material is transformed into a creative product that reflects the individual approach of the student. Thanks to this approach, a comprehensive competence is formed, which includes both practical and communicative skills, as well as the ability to perform professional improvisation.

No less effective innovative method in the professional training of hairdressers is the case method. It allows you to develop analytical thinking and decision-making skills in specific production situations. In the process of working on a case, students analyze situations with different types of hair, select the optimal dyeing or styling techniques, participate in brainstorming, discuss the proposed options and defend their own solutions [4, p. 286-287]. The use of the case method stimulates individual student activity, increases their confidence and motivation to learn, reduces passivity, and forms key professional competencies in future salon service masters. For the teacher, this is an opportunity to update their methodological approaches and creative potential continually. Interactive learning formats, such as discussions and group work, play a crucial role in the training of future hairdressers, particularly when it comes to mastering blond techniques. They create an environment for the active exchange of experiences between students, stimulate interaction, and promote the development of critical thinking. During group discussions, participants can analyze various dyeing and styling techniques, propose

their own solutions and receive feedback from both colleagues and the teacher. This approach not only increases motivation for learning but also develops teamwork skills, the ability to reason and express opinions, and adapt professional techniques to specific situations that arise in the salon.

In the training of future hairdressers, active learning methods play a crucial role, particularly game lessons and role-playing games, which foster emotional involvement among students, develop communication skills, and enable modeling of real client situations [5, p. 105]. During such classes, students develop the ability to concentrate, think independently and show initiative. Thanks to the game format, even the most passive students are actively engaged in educational activities, and a friendly atmosphere is created within the group, leading to increased interest in the profession.

The widespread use of innovative technologies in industrial training lessons, such as excursion lessons, creative laboratories, master classes, roundtables, and work using project methods, contributes to the development of students' research and practical skills [10, p. 195]. Modeling of professional activity, including production tasks, simulators, and simulation exercises, allows students to understand the professional context and develop algorithms for actions in complex production situations. Problem-based learning technologies stimulate creative and critical thinking, teach how to find solutions in non-standard conditions, and project methods ensure the development of responsibility and the achievement of real practical results.

Interactive methods, such as brainstorming, the aquarium or large circle approach, contribute to the collective search for ideas, the development of cooperation skills, and the generation of non-standard approaches in working with clients. Technologies for solving creative and inventive tasks form associative thinking and the ability to predict the results of their activities.

Modern software tools for virtual image selection, such as Cosmopolitan – 102 virtual image maker and Teleport, enable students to safely test hair colors, experiment with shades, and individualize their approach to the client without the risk of errors [7, p. 103]. This combination of gaming, interactive and digital teaching methods ensures the comprehensive development of professional competencies of future hairdressers and adequate preparation for work in a modern salon. The analysis confirms that the implementation of innovative approaches in teaching blond techniques is a key condition for high-quality training of salon service masters. The combination of VR/AR technologies, digital simulators, programs for virtual color selection, and interactive teaching methods enables future specialists to safely practice complex hair lightening techniques, predict the results, and increase the accuracy of their work. The use of game methods, problem-based and project-based learning contributes to the development of creativity, flexible thinking and professional confidence, which is especially important in the field of blond techniques, where mistakes can significantly affect the final result. Thus, innovative pedagogical technologies create conditions for the formation of a competitive master hairdresser, capable of effectively implementing blond techniques in accordance with modern standards of the beauty industry. A visual illustration of the integration of various innovative methods into the process of teaching blond techniques during the professional training of future hairdressers is presented in Fig. 1, which demonstrates how digital technologies, such as VR/AR, simulators and video content, are combined with pedagogical tools - master classes, case methods, game lessons and interactive formats. Such interaction creates a learning environment that simultaneously stimulates creativity, practical skills and motivation of students, preparing them for effective work with clients in real salon service conditions.

Figure 1

Diagram of the main components of innovative methods in teaching blonde methods

Source: author's development

This comprehensive approach to training future hairdressers, where technologies and pedagogical methods work in synergy, demonstrates that the effective combination of VR/AR, simulators, video content, and interactive games with traditional pedagogical methods ensures the development of creativity, practical skills, and readiness to solve real professional tasks in a salon environment. Training becomes more motivating, safe and effective, forming competent and confident specialists.

To enhance the effectiveness of training future hairdressing professionals, it is crucial to integrate diverse innovative methods that consider the unique characteristics of the educational process and the specific needs of students. It is recommended to systematically introduce VR/AR technologies and digital simulators that allow safe and repeated practice of practical skills, as well as contribute to the formation of accuracy and confidence when performing complex procedures. The use of master classes and the case method helps to develop

analytical and creative thinking, and role-playing games, project technologies, and interactive methods stimulate the modeling of real work situations, improving students' communicative and organizational competencies. It is advisable to combine these approaches with video content and online platforms that offer mobile learning, the ability to independently review techniques, and access to materials at any time. Such a comprehensive and adaptive approach not only increases motivation and the speed of mastering complex techniques but also fosters responsibility, independence, and professional flexibility, preparing future masters for a competitive and dynamic labor market.

Conclusions. The study demonstrated that integrating innovative technologies and methods into the training of salon service masters significantly enhances the quality of training, particularly in the area of blond techniques. The use of VR/AR technologies, digital simulators, online platforms, masterclasses, and case studies allows students to practice complex hair lightening techniques without risk to real clients, thereby forming accuracy, confidence, and professional skills. Interactive methods, role-playing games and project technologies contribute to the development of creative and critical thinking, communication skills, independence and motivation to learn. The combination of innovative learning technologies with traditional forms of training is of paramount importance, ensuring the comprehensiveness and systematic development of professional competencies.

Promising areas of further research are related to the development of original program courses, the improvement of integrated forms of practical training and the expansion of the capabilities of digital educational resources.

Thus, the use of innovative pedagogical approaches creates conditions for training a highly qualified, creative, and adaptive specialist who can effectively implement blond techniques and meet the modern requirements of the salon service market.

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